

Australian Research Data Commons

Year in Review 2024

Publication Information

Published:
November 2024

*The Year in Review 2024
covers July 2023 to June 2024*

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13977635

Suggested citation:
ARDC Ltd. Year in Review 2024. Available
from doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13977635

Text
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Acknowledgments

We acknowledge and celebrate the First Australians on whose traditional lands we live and work, and we pay our respects to Elders past, present and emerging.

We'd like to acknowledge all of our members, partners, collaborators and community for their contribution and support — the ARDC would not be possible without you.

ARDC governance

bit.ly/ardc-governance ▶

Meet our ARDC members

bit.ly/ardc-members ▶

Meet our national and international partners

bit.ly/ardc-partners ▶

Our People

Thank you to ARDC staff, partners, and ARDC-supported project and program team members for your contributions.

Contents

A Message From Our Chair	1
A Message From Our CEO	2
ARDC in Numbers	3
Our Strategy	5
Thematic Research Data Commons	7
PEOPLE Research Data Commons	7
PLANET Research Data Commons	9
HUMANITIES, ARTS, SOCIAL SCIENCES (HASS) AND INDIGENOUS Research Data Commons	11
Food Security Data Challenges	13
ARDC Nectar Research Cloud	15
National Information Infrastructure	17
Digital Research Skills	19

A Message from Our Chair

Craig Roy FAICD MBA MSc

Over the past year, the ARDC continued to empower Australian researchers with the data and tools needed to address society's most pressing challenges. We achieved a significant milestone with 47 national data assets and research platforms made available to Australian researchers, along with 12 datasets and tools for research, government and emergency services that address Bushfire Data Challenges.

A few other highlights were establishing new collaborative infrastructure projects in our Thematic Research Data Commons. As part of the People Research Data Commons we delivered Health Data Australia, a new national catalogue of Australian health data for researchers to discover and request access to data for their research. The Planet Research Data Commons is partnering in the next phase of Biosecurity Commons to better meet the urgent needs of biosecurity researchers and decision-makers. The HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons completed its first phase delivering research infrastructure platforms and tools including the Language Data Commons of Australia and the Trove Researcher Guide. We also launched Research Link Australia, a new service for finding information about Australian research and innovation activities.

The ARDC's critical role in supporting Australia's research and innovation system was recognised in the 2023 NCRIS Funding Round, which awarded \$46.4 million, bringing the total Australian Government investment in the ARDC to \$165 million for 2023–2028. This welcome additional funding enables the ARDC to optimise and expand capability in the People, Planet, and HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons.

We will continue to bring together diverse organisations — research institutions, research infrastructure providers, industry, state and federal governments — to provide access to nationally significant, data-intensive digital research infrastructure, platforms, skills and collections of high-quality data.

On behalf of the ARDC board, I thank our team, partners, and the Australian research community. We look forward to continuing to work with you on advancing digital research infrastructure in Australia. ■

A Message from Our CEO

Rosie Hicks

The last 12 months have been a pivotal time for the ARDC. We've seen the highly successful National Data Assets and Platforms programs come to fruition. This significant program of work will add to the digital resources available for researchers, allowing them to focus on the challenges we must solve for a healthy, sustainable future for all Australians.

Indeed, these challenges are recognised in Australia's new National Science and Research Priorities, which include supporting healthy and thriving communities, elevating Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islanders knowledge systems, and protecting and restoring Australia's environment.

We're also seeing digital research infrastructure mature. The recently released National Digital Research Infrastructure Strategy recognises its critical role in supporting Australia's research and innovation system. It is vital that researchers have access to coordinated, robust and enduring digital research infrastructure products and services.

To meet this need, the ARDC is working with the research community to deliver the Thematic Research Data Commons: People, Planet, and HASS and Indigenous. Following extensive national consultations and co-design workshops, major programs of work are now underway across all three RDCs. I'm delighted to share with you some of our successes in this booklet.

As our strategy and program of work progresses, we're focussing on driving uptake of the infrastructure to support researchers. And this includes ensuring that researchers have the skills to use the tools, with over 1,700 training events now listed in Digital Research Skills Australasia (DReSA). Underpinned by the implementation of Australia's first national persistent identifier (PIDs) strategy, our performance measures are expanding to monitor service quality and usage. Ultimately, this will enable us to track the impact of research and demonstrate the benefit of Australia's investment in the research ecosystem.

The National Digital Research Infrastructure Strategy calls for a 'sector-wide data management framework that considers the entire data lifecycle and strategies for storage and accessibility' (p.17). The ARDC looks forward to contributing to the development of a research data framework that preserves nationally significant data assets for generations to come. ■

ARDC in Numbers

PEOPLE Research Data Commons

205

datasets listed
in Health Data
Australia in the
first year

72

organisations
participating in
Health Data Australia
across 9 nodes

PLANET Research Data Commons

400 Users /
Year Growth

1,203 Users

of EcoCommons
Australia

1,600,000 Whole
Audio Files

477,000 Media
Segments

served by Open EcoAcoustics
in the last 90 days

HASS AND INDIGENOUS Research Data Commons

38,786

collections, objects, files and
notebooks in the Language
Data Commons of Australia

532

registrations for
HASS and Indigenous
co-design workshops

Bushfire Data Challenges

11 datasets 18 publications

8 resources **produced for
researchers**

13 **Bushfire Data Challenges
projects delivered**

ARDC Nectar Research Cloud

4,163 Nectar users from 37 Australian universities 14 NCRIS facilities 8 ARC Centres of Excellence

977 users of the ARDC Jupyter Notebook Service

Skills

1,740 Training Events

200+ Current Events

360+ Unique Training Materials

in the DReSA training registry for Australian researchers

7,600

members of the research community attended 104 ARDC-run events

National Information Infrastructure

RAiD

the fourth most common PID mentioned in national PID strategies internationally

781,485

DOIs minted by 76 research organisations

Building on Our Success

48

Platforms and National Data Assets created

156

publications citing these new Platforms and National Data Assets

These figures are from July 2023 to June 2024

ARDC Strategy

Our Purpose

To provide Australian researchers with competitive advantage through data

Our Mission

To accelerate research and innovation by driving excellence in the creation, analysis and retention of high-quality data assets

Our Strategy

Our strategy was developed following extensive nation-wide consultations through which we gained a deep understanding of the research community's needs. It is also aligned with national government priorities. We are delivering leading-edge digital research infrastructure through 3 Thematic Research Data Commons and underpinning national cloud, national information infrastructure and skills activities.

Partnering for Success With Thematic Research Data Commons

In partnership with the research community, the ARDC has established 3 national-scale Thematic Research Data Commons (Thematic RDCs) to meet Australia's future research needs with long-term, enduring digital infrastructure.

Each Thematic RDC integrates the ARDC's underpinning compute, storage infrastructure and services with data assets, analysis platforms and tools. Each is supported by our expertise, skills building activities and our work on developing community-agreed standards and best practices.

These coordinated, structured, and complementary activities are building data assets, tools and skills that will constitute a national 'knowledge infrastructure' that enables Australian researchers to transform our lives.

Co-designed with the research community through extensive consultations and broad partnerships, they will enable us to achieve our goal of supporting the maximum number of researchers in strategic priority areas of research through a new approach to participation and organisation. ■

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mario-purisc - jGz5o7Nc4 / unsplash.com

Strategic Drivers

Underpinning Activities

PEOPLE Research Data Commons

The ARDC People Research Data Commons (People RDC) is delivering national-scale data infrastructure for health research and translation.

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Image - Andy Steven / ARDC

Image - Andy Steven / ARDC

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The People RDC is involving all parts of the health system in national-scale activities, including co-designing frameworks and implementing solutions, to address some of Australia’s core digital health research challenges. We’re delivering research infrastructure in 4 focus areas:

FOCUS AREA 1:
Data Strategy and Data Discovery

FOCUS AREA 3:
Data Integration - Data standards and common models

FOCUS AREA 2:
Secure Data Access - Trusted research environments and data governance

FOCUS AREA 4:
Advanced Analysis - Machine learning, natural language processing, and large language models applied to sensitive health data

Many of the data challenges in health research arise from the sensitive nature of health data and jurisdictional and regulatory requirements that lead to a siloed digital infrastructure ecosystem. The ability to deliver consistent practices, technical interoperability and common standards across this diversity is a defining feature of the People RDC.

The national capabilities in these 4 focus areas will be brought together and applied to improve health services and address specific disease areas.

Be part of the People Research Data Commons

bit.ly/ardc-people ▶

Access resources for health and medical researchers

bit.ly/ardc-people-res ▶

The Impact of Sharing Clinical Research Data

Innovation in healthcare needs compelling evidence synthesised from multiple sources. Whether in the heat of an epidemic or in long-term health systems improvement, the sharing and re-use of clinical data is more important than ever. However, patient privacy and a lack of standardisation often make the process complex or impossible.

To tackle this issue, the ARDC developed the Health Studies Australian National Data Asset (HeSANDA), a program that is creating national infrastructure that enables researchers to readily share and access data from health studies and clinical trials. A component of HeSANDA is Health Data Australia, an online catalogue that contains descriptions of Australian clinical trials data and allows researchers to request access to this data. Since its 2023 launch, over 72 health research organisations nationwide have contributed more than 205 datasets. The establishment of Health Data Australia is in response to the global shift towards data sharing to improve the integrity, productivity, and impact of clinical data.

Senior Research Fellow, Dr Sally Lord, uses secondary clinical trial data in her epidemiological research.

“From a researcher’s perspective: pre-HeSANDA, the broad value of data beyond primary treatment comparisons was well recognised but underused. Now, with HeSANDA facilitating data sharing, I’m looking forward to broader, more cross-disciplinary collaborations for more and higher-impact use,” said Dr Lord.

HeSANDA is a partnership of 9 nodes, representing 72 research organisations across Australia, covering most of Australia’s states, territories, and health researchers. ■

[Through Health Data Australia,] we are making the clinical trial data more visible and creating an infrastructure from which requests to access the data can be made easily. If you share data, you can extend the life and the visibility of your research and facilitate new collaborations. There are many more uses for data, beyond answering the specific focus question that the data was originally collected for.

Professor Angela Webster,
Director of Evidence Integration,
NHMRC Clinical Trials Centre

Learn more about the impact of sharing clinical research data

bit.ly/ardc-hesanda-sharing ▶

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PLANET Research Data Commons

The ARDC Planet Research Data Commons (Planet RDC) provides national-scale data infrastructure for earth and environmental science researchers, policy makers and decision makers.

The Planet RDC brings together research, government and industry to develop systems and processes that make data more available and speed the development of analytics and models. This will help us understand our environment and address some of the most complex, interconnected and integrated challenges facing society.

It leverages the ARDC's decade of expertise in partnering across the research community to deliver earth- and environment-related national data assets and analysis tools that accelerate research.

FOCUS AREA 1:
Trusted Environmental Data and Information Supply Chains

FOCUS AREA 3:
Planet Infrastructure (Networked Modelling, Analytics and Decision Support)

FOCUS AREA 2:
Integrated FAIR Datasets and Services

FOCUS AREA 4:
Governance of Indigenous Data and Skills

The 4 focus areas are integrated through overarching use cases based on the data infrastructure needs of research, government and industry in selected regions or programs of national interest and priority.

Be part of the Planet Research Data Commons
bit.ly/ardc-planet ▶

Access resources for earth and environmental researchers
bit.ly/ardc-planet-res ▶

Improving Australia’s Biosecurity Response to Emerging Threats

Changing climate and increasing globalisation of human movement and trade have dramatically increased Australia’s exposure to new pests and diseases that can have significant economic, environmental, and social impacts. For example, an outbreak of the exotic infectious animal disease, lumpy skin disease, in Australia would impact the beef and dairy industries, harm animal health and welfare, affect food security, and lead to the loss of key export markets.

To address emerging threats, Biosecurity Commons launched in 2023 to help researchers, policymakers and decision makers manage biosecurity risks more effectively. Biosecurity Commons is a partnership between the ARDC, the Centre of Excellence for Biosecurity Risk Analysis (CEBRA) at The University of Melbourne, and various government, research, and industry partners.

Through the ARDC’s Planet Research Data Commons, we’re partnering with Biosecurity Commons to expand its capability and capacity, build real-world use cases, and refine its features to better serve the biosecurity sector.

Biosecurity Commons is being expanded to:

- develop nationally consistent risk analytics for the Australian vegetable industry that can be leveraged by all plant industries through a \$10-million AUSVEG partnership project
- address gaps in risk analysis and modelling of exotic forest pests’ entry into Australia, in collaboration with the Forest and Wood Products Association
- move from a proof-of-concept phase to a trial and evaluation stage through a partnership with the Plant Biosecurity Response Reform at the Australian Government Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (DAFF)
- integrate wildlife camera trap and ecoacoustics data on invasive species through Planet Research Data Commons-supported projects WildObs and EcoAcoustics
- integrate modelling workflows to answer biosecurity policy questions to enhance rapid decision making, with a focus on lumpy skin disease, as part of ARDC’s Food Security Data Challenges. ■

The need for a risk analytics platform like Biosecurity Commons has never been so important. Not only does it provide access to reproducible cutting-edge risk analytics for informing decision making, it also provides tangible benefits in increasing collaboration across industry and governments and building analytical capacity in neighbouring countries. The combination of these I believe will manifest into a more coordinated, efficient and effective biosecurity system.

Dr James Camac,
Senior Research Fellow, Chief Investigator, *CEBRA*,
Project Manager, *Biosecurity Commons*

Learn more about
Biosecurity Commons

bit.ly/biosecurity-commons ▶

Image - G1z5o7NCq4 / unsplash.com

HASS AND INDIGENOUS Research Data Commons

In collaboration with Indigenous Australians, the research community, industry and government, the HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons (HASS and Indigenous RDC) is harnessing research data to enhance Australian social and cultural wellbeing and help Australia understand and preserve our culture, history and heritage.

The HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons has achieved joint resourcing of more than \$40 million over the coming 4 years in partnership with research institutions, non-governmental organisations and government. It is delivering infrastructure in 6 focus areas:

Image - David Hannah / ARDC

**FOCUS AREA 1:
Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities**

**FOCUS AREA 2:
Language Data Commons of Australia**

**FOCUS AREA 3:
Social Sciences**

**FOCUS AREA 4:
Connections**

**FOCUS AREA 5:
Australian Internet Observatory**

**FOCUS AREA 6:
Australian Creative Histories and Futures**

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Image - David Hannah / ARDC

Be a part of the HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons

bit.ly/ardc-hass ▶

Access resources for HASS and Indigenous research data communities

bit.ly/ardc-hass-res ▶

New digital platforms and data directories will improve how researchers discover and access Australia's rich HASS and Indigenous data and innovative analysis tools. The RDC is also upskilling researchers to use data-driven approaches to HASS research and apply Indigenous data governance principles.

The QUT Digital Observatory team had really clear information about what they could do and how they could help. We gave them some search terms and shortly afterwards received a sample of the data so we could check the volume and relevance before pulling the entire database together.

Dr Chris Edwards, Research Fellow, *Aspect Research Centre for Autism Practice (ARCAP)*

Social Media Analysis Reveals That Most People Have No Idea What Autism Is

Elon Musk, Greta Thunberg, Anthony Hopkins – these are some of the public figures who have chosen to publicly share that they are autistic.

While public figures and celebrities are helping to challenge negative stereotypes about autism, a recent study found that for many autistic people, the decision to share, or disclose, their diagnosis/identity with others is fraught with fear and anxiety.

The study was a collaboration of Autism Spectrum Australia (Aspect), Griffith University, the Australian Catholic University, QUT and the University of Sydney. The aim was to better understand the experiences and perspectives of autistic people in relation to autism disclosure.

In a research first, the study used social media data to explore autism disclosure, rather than using traditional methods of interviews and surveys to collect data. They qualitatively analysed 3 years of disclosure-related posts on Twitter and Reddit, sourced via the ARDC-supported Australian Digital Observatory.

Overall, the study concluded, most people in society have no idea what autism is. This creates problems for autistic people on a daily basis in work, dating and healthcare, and can affect their mental health.

The findings emphasise that improving quality of life for autistic people must happen across society. Organisations must urgently become more inclusive at every staff level to support autistic employees, healthcare services must be more inclusive, and we need more positive media portrayals and advocacy through public figures. On top of these changes, the researchers recommend that we need to make it everyone's responsibility to promote a more inclusive society while respecting the confidentiality of autism disclosures, shifting the emotional burden of disclosure from 'them' to 'us', and reducing the spread of misinformation.

The Australian Digital Observatory project partners were the ARDC, The University of Melbourne, UNSW, The University of Queensland, and the Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation (QCIF), with QUT as the lead node.

The Australian Digital Observatory is now part of a new 4-year national research infrastructure project, the Australian Internet Observatory, which aims to enhance the availability and usability of internet data. ■

Learn more about the case study

bit.ly/ardc-autism ►

Food Security Data Challenges

To enhance research into food production, supply, consumption and waste, the ARDC launched the Food Security Data Challenges in 2022. The program addresses the challenge of sustainable development, with an initial focus on food security.

Food Security Data Challenges is part of the ARDC’s Translational Research Data Challenges initiative, which provides innovative, digital infrastructure solutions to real-world problems.

To identify priority areas to address through Food Security Data Challenges, we conducted an 11-month consultation process involving more than 300 stakeholders from over 130 organisations including research, government and industry. Ten Food Security Data Challenges projects are now underway, supported by \$4.6 million in ARDC co-investment and \$7 million co-investment from project partners.

The 10 projects within Food Security Data Challenges encompass a variety of areas, including agriculture, fisheries, food equity, biosecurity, nutrition, food provenance and traceability as well as cross-cutting topics such as data aggregation and visualisation, data governance and secure data sharing.

Learn more about Food Security Data Challenges

bit.ly/ardc-food ▶

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Just like we have standard residential tenancy contracts, an industry standard data sharing agreement to protect farm businesses provides assurance and protection.

Gabi Ceregra,
Data Policy Manager,
Food Agility CRC

New Online Tool Simplifies Farm Data Sharing Contracts

It is now easier for farm businesses and those who collect, manage and share their data to access an industry best-practice contract for data sharing – thanks to a new digital tool.

The online Data Sharing Agreement (DSA) Tool is free to use and has been developed through the Data Sharing Initiative project, a partnership between Food Agility CRC, tier one legal firm Minter Ellison, Federation University and the ARDC.

Data use and sharing is important for improving the productivity of farming, but producers need assurance about how their data is collected and used.

The DSA Tool digitises the hard-copy Data Sharing Agreement Template that was developed in the project, making it easier for users to customise data sharing contracts.

“It’s designed for contracts with only a few parties, for example a farm business and a research institute. The tool can be used to inform any other data sharing contracts such as software terms and conditions, or non-farm business contracts between collaborators or project partners,” said Food Agility CRC Data Policy Manager Gabi Ceregra.

The DSA Tool has been 3 years in the making, with feedback received from across the agricultural industry. It’s also aligned with the National Farmers’ Federation’s Australian Farm Data Code (the Code) to provide data protections for farmers.

The DSA Tool is accompanied by a certification program that aims to create trust and improve transparency when providers meet all the criteria of the Code. The project partners are also providing training to the food and agricultural industries about the Code and certification process. This training educates food producers about the value of their data, best practices for data management, and the benefits of the certification process.

By fostering greater transparency between providers and food producers, this project empowers farmers and food producers to securely and confidently share their data. ■

Image - AKySQZrcd6Q / unsplash.com

Image - xMh_mw8HN_Q / unsplash.com

Learn more about the Data Sharing Initiative

bit.ly/ardc-dsi ►

ARDC Nectar Research Cloud

The ARDC Nectar Research Cloud is Australia’s national research cloud, specifically designed for research computing. It provides Australia’s research community with fast, interactive, self-service access to large-scale computing infrastructure, software and data. A powerful platform for collaboration, it allows researchers and research support staff to access compute resources, software and data from their offices and homes and easily share them with collaborators at other institutions. It also powers other national ARDC services.

ARDC Services Powered by Nectar

A wide range of national services are available via Nectar to save time, boost productivity, facilitate collaboration and power groundbreaking research.

Virtual Desktop Service

This service gives researchers an extra personal computer in the cloud. It’s a simple way to access Nectar compute resources.

Jupyter Notebook Service

Develop, combine and export computational notebooks and interactive visualisations in pre-configured computing environments, such as Python, R and SciPy.

BinderHub Service

This managed service turns code, data and computational environments into shareable, executable and reproducible Binder environments that can easily be used by collaborators and colleagues.

National GPU Service

Easily reserve GPUs and large-memory virtual machines for demanding research activities like processing large datasets, 3D imaging, machine learning and computational modelling.

Get started with the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud and services

bit.ly/ardc-nectar ►

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Image - loic le gully / ARDC

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[Nectar] allows us to have a hosting platform that is independent of any of the partner organisations in the collaboration. Most critically, it lets us keep our applications online during gaps between funded stages of the project. Also, the Nectar support teams have always been really helpful, and the training resources they provide are just getting better and better.

Sharon Tickell,
Senior Software Engineer,
CSIRO

Accelerating Great Barrier Reef Research and Preservation

The Great Barrier Reef is without doubt one of Australia’s and the world’s most spectacular and important natural assets, but it is under serious threat. In the Australian and Queensland governments’ Reef 2050 Long-Term Sustainability Plan, land-based run-off, coastal development, human use and most of all, climate change are identified as the 4 main threats to the Reef.

To help with reporting and decision making around preserving the Reef, the Great Barrier Reef Foundation, CSIRO, Australian Institute of Marine Science, Bureau of Meteorology, and Queensland Government have collaborated to develop the eReefs platform. Currently funded by the Reef Trust Partnership, the platform has been used to model the physical, chemical and optical properties of the Reef waters. It then provides access to the results and associated data and visualisation products.

Since eReefs’ inception in 2012, Nectar has hosted its data access and visualisation applications. These include the eReefs Data Explorer, which visualises key data products including model results and processed satellite imagery for oil spills detection and water quality monitoring, both delivered by CSIRO. These earth observation products are crucial to understanding and responding to pollution and the overall water quality of the Reef.

Sharon Tickell, who leads the development and support for eReefs’ web platforms at CSIRO, said that Nectar has been “an incredible resource for enabling public delivery of science applications”. ■

Learn more about the case study
bit.ly/ardc-nectar-story

National Information Infrastructure

To accelerate research and underpin research integrity, the ARDC provides high value, contemporary and enduring services for the discovery, linkage and interoperability of data. These services support the discovery and use of data, software, instruments and tools with related information on grants, projects, publications, authors and contributors.

ARDC Research Data Australia - a national catalogue for international scale data findability. Researchers can contribute, find, access, and reuse data and related materials sourced from over 100 Australian research organisations, government agencies and cultural institutions.

Health Data Australia - a national catalogue of Australian health data. Search for and request access to clinical trials datasets collected across Australia by universities, medical research institutes, clinical trials networks and health services.

ARDC Research Link Australia - a national service linking information about research from research, government and industry. By bridging the information gap between these key areas, research and industry can discover opportunities for collaboration and innovation that support research translation.

ARDC Research Vocabularies Australia - a national vocabulary service to promote semantic interoperability. It helps researchers to create, manage, find and access community vocabularies, which make the meaning of research data explicit and enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

Persistent Identifier Services - provided to Australian research institutions free of charge so they can support researchers with citation and attribution of their research. Our PID services are offered in partnership with international PID providers to connect researchers and their data, projects and institutions into the global knowledge base. We provide 4 international standard PID services: Digital Object Identifier (DOI), Handles, International Generic Sample Number (IGSN), and Research Activity Identifier (RAiD). These identifiers may be linked to a researcher's ORCID record.

RAiD - a global persistent identifier system to identify, discover, track and administer research projects. RAiD is an ISO standard (23527:2022) and the ARDC is the ISO-appointed global Registration Authority. The RAiD system stores, updates, shares and links project metadata information with the global research community, facilitating the administration and reporting of project information. The ARDC and DOI registration agency DataCite are partnering to deliver RAiD services. RAiD is being integrated with European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) infrastructure.

Learn more about our research data and information services

bit.ly/ardc-services ►

Australian National Persistent Identifier (PID) Strategy: Accelerating Research and Innovation

In February 2024, the ARDC released the Australian National Persistent Identifier (PID) Strategy, a coordinated, comprehensive and collaborative approach to accelerate Australian research and innovation through universal use of connected Persistent Identifiers (PIDs).

The report *Incentives to Invest in Identifiers*, commissioned by the ARDC and the AAF, finds significant savings to the Australian research system with a coordinated, comprehensive and collaborative approach to PIDs in place. It estimates potential savings of up to \$24 million per annum along with 38,000 person days that could be freed up from re-keying information that PIDs provide.

There is growing momentum nationally and internationally to better leverage data stemming from research and about research and to harness the potential offered by PIDs. Many countries, including the UK and Canada, have begun developing a national approach to PIDs to underpin their research and innovation ecosystems.

Overall, the Strategy will help us better understand Australia’s research capability to address the nation’s pressing economic, social, health and environmental challenges by mapping our researchers, organisations, research services and infrastructure.

Linda O’Brien,
Previous Chair,
International ORCID Board

In light of the benefits of PIDs, the ARDC led a coordinated, comprehensive and collaborative process to develop a national PID strategy for Australia. Guided by a National PID Strategy Taskforce of key sector stakeholders, the process involved extensive consultation through national workshops, working groups, webinars and an open call for individual and group submissions. A draft Strategy was released in July 2023 and refined through extensive and open co-design, consultation and engagement with the sector.

The final Strategy, presented by the ARDC’s CEO Rosie Hicks at the February 2024 Universities Australia Deputy Vice Chancellors-Research (DVC-R) meeting, sets the vision to “accelerate Australian research quality, efficiency and impact through universal use of connected persistent identifiers”.

Implementing the National PID Strategy

The Strategy is being implemented through a national collaborative roadmap - a co-design process with the research community to develop and collaborate on action plans that advance the PIDs agenda. ■

Get involved in the Roadmap development

bit.ly/pid-roadmap ►

Digital Research Skills

The ARDC provides national leadership in building digital research skills, working together with research communities, institutions and infrastructure providers. This collaboration equips both the research and the research infrastructure workforce with the skills required to effectively use digital research platforms, services and tools now and into the future.

Learn about our national leadership in digital research skills
bit.ly/ardc-skills

Images - David Hannah / ARDC

Powering Research Through Skills

A nationally coordinated approach to digital research skills development provides Australia's researchers with a globally competitive edge.

In the past year, the ARDC enabled national coordination and collaboration on digital research skills development by hosting annual events. The primary event - the ARDC Digital Research Skills Summit - was held in May 2024, bringing together over 100 people from the digital research trainer community, ARDC co-investment project partners, NCRIS facilities and research institutions. They shared their experiences in developing digital research skills and engaging infrastructure users through training activities to identify the skills Australian researchers need and how best to deliver training to achieve cutting-edge research.

The Summit provided me with valuable opportunities to learn more about the ways that digital research infrastructure can inform community-engaged research and teaching in ways that enrich but also transcend national contexts, conventions, and scholarly networks ... The ARDC has certainly helped shape our ongoing efforts in these directions.

Dr Graham Jensen,

Assistant Director and Mitacs Accelerate Postdoctoral Fellow in Open, Collaborative Scholarship (Arts & Humanities) in the Electronic Textual Cultures Lab (ETCL), *University of Victoria, Canada*

Another national approach to skills coordination is the development and refinement of the ARDC Digital Research Capabilities and Skills Framework. The Skills Framework enables the research sector to analyse the need for digital research skills, and how to respond to demand and areas of deficit. It opens the door to new approaches to skills and workforce development strategies, training and learning pathways, and policy development and implementation.

Our coordinated approach to digital research capabilities, skills and workforce development has been recognised internationally. We are working with Canadian and European counterparts keen to adopt and implement the ARDC's Skills Framework and other national initiatives, such as the Digital Research Skills Australasia (DReSA) training registry.

DReSA continued to grow this year and now lists a back catalogue of 1,740 training events, over 200 current events and 360 unique training materials on digital research skills. DReSA is run in partnership with Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre and the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) to provide an open online registry for researchers to discover digital research training events, materials, providers and trainers in Australia and New Zealand. ■

Australian Research Data Commons

MEMBERS

HEAD OFFICE

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900 Dandenong Road, Caulfield East, VIC 3145

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